

Drought resistance

Dryland rice selections for drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India

N. C. Basu Raychaudhuri, Rice Research Station, Bankura, India

Drought is the most serious problem for rainfed dryland rice areas of West Bengal, India's leading rice-growing state. New semidwarf varieties have made little impact because they cannot tolerate moisture stress.

Rice areas in the 2 worst affected districts, Bankura and Purulia, are about 380,000 and 230,000 ha. A single crop of rainfed rice is the main livelihood of the farmers; dryland rice accounts for more than 60% of the rice lands. Among the main causes of low yields are short and uneven rainfall distribution, undulating land, and poor soil moisture retention.

Work on dryland rice improvement was undertaken at Bankura and Purulia. A number of field screening tests using cultivars obtained through the International Rice Testing Program (IRTP) were followed by yield potential tests. For 2 years (1976 and 1977), more than 200 dryland rice cultivars from different

Promising dryland cultivars for the drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India.

Designation	Origin	Maturity (days)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Drought reaction ^a
B9c-Md-3	Indonesia	99	96	4.1	3
IR2061-522-6-9	IRRI	104	114	3.7	3
IET1444	India	103	92	3.6	3
CR141-192	India	100	105	3.5	1
CR125-17	India	89	88	3.5	3
Se. 302-G	Senegal	90	82	3.5	3
CR143-2-2	India	102	95	3.4	3
DV110	Bangladesh	105	136	3.4	3
RC7046	India	102	132	3.3	3
Panke	India	101	142	3.3	1
ARC7060	India	89	146	3.3	1
Se. 322 B19	Senegal	89	80	3.2	1
FH109	India	103	99	3.2	3
Brown Gora	India	93	132	3.2	1
CTG1516	Bangladesh	100	140	2.9	1

^aAt reproductive stage. 1 = none to slight effect of stress, 3 = moderate effect of stress (leaf tip drying up to 3/4 length of leaves).

countries were tested in duplicate sets in the two districts on a typical coarse sandy loam soil with poor moisture retention.

Visual scoring of drought resistance and recovery and effects of drought on growth and yield components were periodically recorded according to the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

More than 50% of the entries, mostly

tall traditional types, were tolerant of drought. After rigorous screening, 24 early-maturing (105 days) and 24 medium-maturing types (106–125 days) were selected and tested for yield potential. The most promising (see table) have been further tested in adaptive trials and minikit plots in different locations, and results are encouraging. ■

The line source sprinkler: a new research tool for drought screening

J. C. O'Toole and D. W. Puckridge, Agronomy Department, International Rice Research Institute

A new research technique, the line source sprinkler, was evaluated at IRRI for use in drought resistance screening in the 1979 dry season. Figure 1 illustrates the field installation, which consists of full-circle sprinklers spaced at intervals of 6.1 m (20-ft pipe section). The system produces a linear decrease in the amount of water applied with distance away from the line (Fig. 2). Also shown in Figure 2 are some crop responses to varying amounts of applied irrigation water.

1. Schematic of the field layout of sprinklers in the source sprinkler technique.